

A Study on the Effect of Various Factors on the Slope, S_v , of Some Tetraalkylammonium Iodides in Some Nonaqueous Solvents

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From the available data on apparent molal volume, φ_v , in various solvents at different concentrations for different tetraalkylammonium iodides φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves are plotted and the values of slope, S_v , are obtained in the usual manner. A comparative study of the results in different solvents for a particular electrolyte and also for different R_4NI salts in a particular solvent indicates that the slope, S_v , decreases with the increase in the dielectric constant of the medium as well as with the increasing size of tetraalkylammonium ion with few exceptions; hydrogen bonding does not have any significant effect on the slope, S_v , values.

ONE of the fascinating subjects of study during the past few years has been the investigation of apparent molal volume of tetraalkylammonium and common salts in aqueous and nonaqueous solutions. The slope, S_v , of the φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves has been found to be positive for some electrolytes while negative for others in different solvents. In aqueous solution positive slope of φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves for common electrolytes as well as for tetraalkylammonium halides containing smaller R_4N^+ ions e.g., Me_4N^+ and Et_4N^+ and negative slope for the salts containing larger R_4N^+ ions at ordinary concentrations have been reported¹⁻⁴. The negative slope in water has been explained by many workers⁵⁻⁷ on the basis of enhancement of tetrahedral structure of water by hydrophobic R_4N^+ -water interaction. This explanation seems to be not very convincing when the negative slopes have also been obtained for some $R_4N^+X^-$ salts in some nonaqueous solvents like formamide, N-methylacetamide (NMA) and N-methylpropionamide (NMP)⁸⁻¹⁰ etc. in which neither tetrahedral structure is present nor the hydrophobic interaction is expected.

Gopal and Siddiqi⁹ suggested that the negative slope occurs if the volume of the solute ion is comparatively large as compared to the solvent molecule and if the interpenetration of the ions take place¹¹. Gopal, Singh and Siddiqi¹² have also explained the negative slope obtained for some small and compact common ions in NMP and NMA on the basis that small solute ions are accommodated in the voids left in the packing of the solvent molecules.

Thus different explanations have been given for the positive and negative nature of the slope, S_v , of φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves in case of different electrolytes in various types of the solvents, but none of them seem to be satisfactory for all types of the solutes

and solvents. Since now sufficient φ_v data of R_4NI salts at different concentrations are available from which S_v values can be obtained by plotting φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ in different solvents of varying dielectric constant, it seems desirable to tabulate them at a place and to see how the S_v values depend upon the physical properties of the solvent like dielectric constant, hydrogen bonding etc. and on the size of the ion. In the present communication, an attempt has been made to study the effect of dielectric constant, hydrogen bonding of the solvent and the varying sizes of the ion on the slope, S_v of the φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves.

Results and Discussion

From the φ_v data obtained by our group^{8,10,12}, for tetraalkylammonium iodides in solvents of varying dielectric constant namely formamide, NMA, NMP, DMSO, PC and EC†, φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves have been drawn and the slope, S_v , has been calculated in each case. The S_v values thus obtained have been listed in Tables 1 and 2. Table 1 consists of S_v values in nonhydrogen bonded solvents whereas table 2 contains that in hydrogen bonded solvents.

Effect of dielectric constant on slope, S_v

From the tables 1 and 2, it may be noted that a comparison of S_v values for a particular R_4NI salt in Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), Propylene carbonate (PC) and Ethylene carbonate (EC) on one hand and in Formamide, N-methylpropionamide (NMP) and N-methylacetamide (NMA) on the other hand indicate that S_v decreases with the increase in dielectric constant of the solvent provided that the solvents are of similar nature in some properties like dipole moment, hydrogen bonding etc.

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† NMA = N-methylacetamide; NMP = N-methylpropionamide; DMSO = Dimethylsulfoxide,

PC = Propylene carbonate; EC = Ethylene-carbonate.

TABLE 1— S_v VALUES OF SOME R_4NI SALTS IN SOME NONHYDROGEN BONDED SOLVENTS AT 40°C

Solvent	S_v value for				
	Et ₄ NI	Pr ₄ NI	Bu ₄ NI	Pen ₄ NI	Hep ₄ NI
Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 46.6$)	6.4	8.3	8.8	9.0	9.5
Propylene-carbonate (PC) ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 64.72$)	4.7	4.5	4.2	4.0	3.6
Ethylene carbonate (EC) ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 95.30$)	1.9	-1.5	-2.8	-4.0	-5.9

TABLE 2— S_v VALUES OF SOME R_4NI SALTS IN SOME HYDROGEN BONDED SOLVENTS AT 40°C

Solvent	S_v value for				
	Et ₄ NI	Pr ₄ NI	Bu ₄ NI	Pen ₄ NI	Hep ₄ NI
Formamide ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 109.5$)	4.2	8.3	9.2	-6.6	-6.8
N-methylpropionamide (NMP) ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 176.0$)	—	3.3	-1.2	-1.4	-1.6
N-methylacetamide (NMA) ($\epsilon_{25}^\circ = 185$)	2.6	2.4	-7.0	-2.3	-2.0

The S_v values given in tables 1 and 2 are plotted against dielectric constant of the solvent and illustrative examples of the plots are demonstrated for Pr₄NI in figures 1 and 2, from which it is clear that a straight line is obtained in every case indicating direct dependence of slope, S_v , on dielectric constant of the solvent. This variation of S_v with dielectric constant may be explained on the basis that in case of solvents of medium and low dielectric constant, electrostatic interionic attraction will be appreciable and an ion is supposed to have strong influence on its neighbours. The extent of this

interaction would depend upon concentration. This effect coupled with ion-solvent interaction although weak appears to be responsible for the positive value of S_v . While in the solvents of high dielectric constant (> 70), the electrolyte may assume to be completely ionised even at fairly high concentrations. The mutual penetration of the R_4N^+ ions and their penetration by I⁻ ions as well as entrapping^{13,14} of the solvent molecules in the voids formed by the larger R_4N^+ ions seem to be in general responsible for the negative slope in the ϕ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves in these solvents of high dielectric constant.

Fig. 1. Dielectric constant (ϵ) dependence of slope, S_v , of Pr₄NI in some nonhydrogen bonded solvents.

Fig. 2. Dielectric constant (ϵ) dependence of slope, S_v of Pr_4NI in some hydrogen bonded solvents.

Effect of hydrogen bonding of the solvent on S_v values

From the tables 1 and 2, it may be noted that hydrogen bonding of the solvent has no significant effect on the S_v values. It is supported by the results of Padova *et al.*¹⁵, who have reported positive slope of φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves for all the tetraalkylammonium salts studied in methyl alcohol having sufficient hydrogen bonding. If hydrogen bonding has significant effect on S_v values then the slope of φ_v vs. $\sqrt{C}$ curves for larger tetraalkylammonium salts must be negative in methyl alcohol.

Effect of the size of the ion on S_v values

From these studies, it is evident that in most of the cases the S_v values decreases with increasing size of the ion in a particular solvent. The slope becomes negative if the difference between the size of the ion and solvent molecule is too much. This is because of the fact that the chances of accommodation of solvent molecules in the voids formed by larger R_4N^+ ions are fairly good, if the size of the ions are larger than that of solvent molecules and vice versa.

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